

ON THE DAMPING PROPERTIES OF LOAD-BEARING BIOLOGICAL MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

A key function of load-bearing biological materials, such as bone and sea shell, is to protect their inside fragile organs by effectively damping dynamic impact. How those materials achieve this remarkable function remains largely unknown. Through the finite element simulation and theoretical modeling, the stress wave propagation and attenuation in the load-bearing biological materials were investigated, and the roles of biopolymer viscosity, structural arrangement, mineral volume fraction and hierarchical design were analysed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Load-bearing biological materials in reality are mainly exposed to dynamical loadings like external impact, but most of the existing works have been focused on static loading conditions. For example, loadings on bones are often dynamic arising from jumping, running, sporting and fighting activities as well as impacting from external objects. Unlike static loadings, dynamic loadings generate stress waves which can transmit the kinetic energy from the loading boundary deep inside and even throughout bone to cause damage to the inside fragile tissue. Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is just a good example which results from stress waves reaching brain but often without breaking skull. Therefore, it is expected that high loss viscoelasticity should be an important property for these load-bearing biological materials to efficiently damp stress wave and protect their inside soft organs from various external dynamic loads. Exploring the damping behaviors and their relations with the architectures in these load-bearing biological materials not only can add insights into the mechanism of their protection functions, but also can provide useful guidelines for developing high loss viscoelastic composites which are highly desired in many industry areas including vehicle, military, and etc.

2 METHODOLOGY

Using systematic finite element analyses, we studied the stress wave propagation and attenuation in cortical bone at the nanoscale as a model material to examine the effects of protein viscosity, mineral fraction and staggered architecture on the elastic wave decay. As shown in Figure 1, a staggered composite (a) widely seen in load-bearing biological materials was modelled, with comparison with its layered counterpart (b); the loading was a temporal impact loading (c) applied on the left ($x=0$) or top ($y=0$) boundary of the composite; a typical unit cell with generated structural mesh was given in (d).

Figure 1: Schematics of (a) a staggered structure widely seen in load-bearing biological materials and (b) its layered counterpart, (c) impact loading applied on the left ($x=0$) or top ($y=0$) boundary of the structures and their corresponding mechanical models (the insets), and (d) a sample unit cell with generated structural mesh.

With a self-similar hierarchical model (see Figure 2), a theoretical approach was established to investigate the damping properties of load-bearing biological materials in relation to the biopolymer viscous characteristics, the loading frequency, the geometrical parameters of reinforcements, as well as the hierarchy number. According to the correspondence principle of viscoelasticity, the following recursive formulae were derived for the storage and loss modulus of the composite at every level of structural hierarchy, respectively,

Figure 2: The self-similar hierarchical model for typical load-bearing biological materials.

$$E_{s(n)} = \frac{\alpha^2 \rho^4 \phi (G_{sP}^2 E_{s(n-1)} + E_{s(n-1)} G_{IP}^2) + 4\alpha \rho^2 (1-\phi) (E_{s(n-1)}^2 G_{sP} + G_{sP} E_{l(n-1)}^2)}{[\alpha \rho^2 G_{sP} - 4(1-1/\phi) E_{s(n-1)}]^2 + [\alpha \rho^2 G_{IP} - 4(1-1/\phi) E_{l(n-1)}]^2} \quad (1)$$

$$E_{l(n)} = \frac{\alpha^2 \rho^4 \phi (E_{l(n-1)} G_{sP}^2 + E_{l(n-1)} G_{IP}^2) + 4\alpha \rho^2 (1-\phi) G_{IP} (E_{s(n-1)}^2 + E_{l(n-1)}^2)}{[\alpha \rho^2 G_{sP} - 4(1-1/\phi) E_{s(n-1)}]^2 + [\alpha \rho^2 G_{IP} - 4(1-1/\phi) E_{l(n-1)}]^2} \quad (2)$$

where $n=1, \dots, N$, N is the total hierarchy number of the composite, and the subscripts n and $n-1$ denote the sequence number of structural hierarchy; ρ and ϕ are, respectively, the aspect ratio and volume fraction of the hard inclusion at each individual level, and ϕ is related to the mineral volume fraction of the hierarchical composite, φ , by $\phi = \sqrt[N]{\varphi}$; G_{sP} and G_{IP} are the storage and loss shear modulus of viscoelastic biopolymer, respectively, and α is a factor representing the stiffness contribution of the matrix in the tension regions. It should be noted that the biopolymer characteristic is assumed the same for different levels of structural hierarchy, i.e., the only one type of biopolymer (for example the protein of Type I collagen) is adopted as the soft matrix in the hierarchical model.

3 MAJOR FINDINGS

1) There are two basic mechanisms for a typical biological material to fast attenuate stress wave over its travelling distance: one is stress wave scattering due to the soft-hard interfaces, and the other is kinetic energy dissipation due to the viscosity of biopolymer components. Our study here suggests that the nanostructure of bone very well synergizes the two mechanisms to achieve fast stress wave attenuation.

2) Adopting the characteristic relaxation time to measure the viscoelastic property of biopolymer matrix (like collagen), it was found that, given a specific volume fraction of mineral (biopolymer), there is a critical characteristic relaxation time, below which the viscosity-based energy-dissipation mechanism predominantly dictates the stress wave attenuation so that the contribution from the structure-based interface scattering mechanism is trivial, whereas above which, structure optimization (from a layered structure to an optimal staggered in the current paper) will be important and necessary to enhance the stress wave attenuation as the contribution from the structure-based interface scattering mechanism is nontrivial but crucial. The principle applies to bone soundly: the typical characteristic relaxation time of collagen is above the critical value, and bone adopts the delicate staggered structure even in the presence of viscous protein. On the other hand, our finding here rationalizes the staggered arrangement widely seen in load-biological materials in the perspective of dynamics.

3) Regarding the staggered nanocomposites in bone, we found that an optimal staggered structure with specific feature sizes and geometrical layouts exists leading to the fastest wave decay. Importantly, the optimal feature sizes and geometrical layouts predicted by our simulations are in excellent agreement with the experimental observations in the literature.

4) The roles of biopolymer viscosity, mineral volume fraction and structural arrangement are recognized regarding the capability of stress wave attenuation of load-bearing biological materials, and it is found that the stress wave attenuation would gradually become structure-insensitive as the biopolymer viscosity or the mineral volume fraction increases. In the structure-sensitive regime, structural arrangement of mineral platelets plays a significant role in enhancing the stress wave attenuation, and hence a detailed optimization of structural arrangement is needed to acquire a superior capability in attenuating stress waves. In contrary, in the structure-insensitive regime, structural arrangement of mineral platelets plays a trivial role, and thus a detailed optimization of structural arrangement is unnecessary.

5) Hierarchical design also plays an important role in the damping properties of load-bearing biological materials. Specifically, the damping behavior of load-bearing biological materials mainly originates from the viscous characteristics of the organic (biopolymer) constituents, but it is greatly tuned and enhanced by the staggered and hierarchical organization of the organic and inorganic

constituents

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